

International, Joint, & Online programs

An overview of concepts
and some options for
KyotoU

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1. Introduction

International, joint, and Online education none of these concepts are new however it is the *combination of the three* that has gained increasing visibility particularly since the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic in early 2020.

International academic cooperation has a long history that in today's world realizes through agreements and exchanges aimed at boosting the students' exposure to different ideas, enhancing innovation and dealing with diversity.

Joint or dual academic programs aim to address the needs of students with specific career goals and with strong interests in two disciplines. These programs have a wide range of characteristics depending on how they are built and they may be offered by a single university or by partnerships, sometimes located abroad.

Online education has gained increasing visibility in the last couple of decades. Although it used to "*suffer from lack of trust*" from academics, governments and employers, the situation has changed as legal or administrative restrictions at the ministerial and universities levels as well as in the access to jobs in by graduates have decreased. The COVID-19 pandemic greatly contributed to this change as previous attitudes and distrust by governments and universities have had to come to terms with remote learning and the use of digital technologies.

Although scope and nature of international joint online programs vary depending on the combination of elements such as level (graduate or postgraduate), for degree or not for degree, for pay or for free, etc. they share key aspects such as offering degrees or certificates that serve as evidence of participation and achievements of the common goal of creating better and more up-to-date learning opportunities.

By combining the 3 concepts (international, joint, and online) universities create programs resulting for example in *virtual joint programs*, (2 or more institutions offer a program online); or *online international programs*, (a university offers an online program for international audiences), or *joint international programs* (2 or more universities offer double or joint degrees based on international physical mobility).

The growth in *opportunities is clear*, but *there are challenges* that include quality assurance, securing financial resources, or legal restrictions, and new issues like safety in the access to education, cyber security and inclusion in terms of access to academic and technical resources by academic partners as well as the targeted students.

Other key issues *include legal recognition by states of international, joint, and online diplomas*; whereby acceptance of degrees and licensing continues to be largely disperse. This particularly the case of certain fields, such as law and medicine.

The variety of *degrees and diplomas around the world* make it difficult to grasp the real value of these degrees when put in a global context. For instance, different definitions apply to what an *academic bachelor* as compared to an *executive bachelor diploma* are; or similarly any other higher diploma such as a *professional degree*. The same applies to masters and *PHD degrees*.

New graduates need to be ready to address the demands from the job markets, and to that end universities must offer the kind of education that is required: relevance of contents, skill sets and delivery methods (offer quality education, that is accessible and safe).

Providing *international, joint and online* programs became a natural strategy to address the increasing demands from students and employers. And to keep up with those demands, universities need to be creative in *what and how they offer it*.

International, joint, and online programs is a clear tendency, however the distinctions in what these concepts mean and the implications on how those programs are designed and implemented vary greatly.

The challenge is: how to provide remote learning that is accessible to wider audiences, while ensuring that education of high quality is provided. This also relates to other factors such as having enough number of well-prepared teachers, sufficient technical infrastructures and support, well-designed curricula and evaluation methods, etc.

About this paper

This is papers is a literature review converging aspects of what *International, Joint and Online* programs are, taken as individual aspects of different educational programs and then, as an integrated option, meaning programs that contain all three features.

The paper supports KyotoU's commitment to provide innovative and high-quality education, while promoting independent and interactive learning; while also contributing to KyotoU's engagement with society by means of expanding access to its educational opportunities.

International, joint, online programs are an excellent way for KyotoU to continue promoting foreign academic exchange and striving to contribute to making a better world. More specifically, since these programs directly align with the commitment of KyotoU to the goals of Top Global University Program targeted for Year 2023. Namely:

- Education and research guidance provided by world-class researchers
- Increasing inbound and outbound student mobility
- Establishing international joint education/degree programs
- Expanding the network with overseas world-leading universities
- MOOC to attract high-potential students from around the world
- Raising the ratio of lectures taught in English
- Boosting multinational academic papers authored by students
- Enhancing support for international students and students studying abroad

This paper represents a response to the current situation by focusing on KyotoU's needs and expectations but also on its accumulated experience and resources. This paper should serve as a starting point for discussion regarding the need, role and capabilities for the university to consolidate, expand or create new international joint online programs.

Based on key examples, an overview of what an "integrated" international joint online program is, and the key elements and decisions that need to be addressed at the time of creating such programs. Some level of focus is given to COIL (Collaborative Online International Learning) programs and a new form of response. The paper offers a brief inventory of existing programs in KyotoU; suggestions for consolidation, expansion and creation of new programs; an overview of challenges. A list of references serves as a general resources used, and it includes a list of ongoing programs serving as good practices.

2. *International* programs

Features, Pros & Cons

- 2 of more elements in the educational relation are located abroad.
- There exist multiple types and layers: E.g. temporary exchanges, for and not-for degree, at all levels (pre-graduate, graduate, postgraduate), etc.
- Cross-cultural perspectives are highly valued and purposely highlighted.
- physical mobility typically is required, and the *travel component* is fun but expensive.
- Issues with QA and recognition of credits and degrees require direct attention.
- Language barriers may exist in setting and implementing the program. This holds true for teachers, students and support administrative staff.
- The use of English as *lingua franca* is extended but not the only solution
- Strong student support system required at both ends (outbound and inbound) for logistics and legal matters, e.g. lodging, transportation and visas.
- Formal agreements are typically necessary. E.g. MOUs or SEAs
- Participation may be bilateral or multilateral: 2 or more countries involve
- For degrees or not for degree, single or multiple diplomas: credit transfer, JD, DD
- International and cultural exposure is typically fostered as an integral component
- Cross-cultural activities are imbedded as curricular and non curricular activities
- physical mobility is required but also internationalization at home is a key element
- International recognition degrees and certificates may be thorny.
- Support for students in academic matters may be needed. E.g. learning agreement.
- Reliance on mutual complementarity of partners in their academic offer

Concrete examples

- In KyotoU: Courses in Top Global Initiative: Japan Gateway: Top Global Program.
- In KyotoU: 156 SEAs as of April 2020
- In KyotoU: University wide MOUs with 180 universities, 4 university alliances and 15 other institutions (199 in total) in 55 different countries and regions. As of November 24, 2020
- In KyotoU: Extensive network of Department level MOUs and SEAs.
- International Study Programs at Tokyo Tech. Dual and Joint Undergrad. Programs
- Johns Hopkins University Program in International Studies + Sciences Po Paris. BA/MA Program in International Studies
- Columbia University Alliance: Columbia University, École Polytechnique, Sciences Po, and Paris 1 Panthéon-Sorbonne University.
- Multilateral arrangements such as Erasmus, UMAP, AIMS Programme Etc.
- Campus Asia Consortium (China, Japan, Korea)

3. Joint programs

Features, Pros & Cons

- Diversity of diplomas. E.g. a single (joint) or multiple (double) degree is granted by two or more universities; or as a dual degree (2 or more degrees by one university)
- Based on mutual agreement. E.g. MOU with terms and distribution of tasks, aiming at achieving shared goals, objectives, financial and human resources, etc.
- Credit-bearing courses: accreditation, transfer, recognition.
- Partners share an pool educational resources to complement each other's resources and expertise to develop programs t based on partners' strengths.
- Issues with QS need to be addressed. I.e. dealing with national degree agencies.
- Actual mobility is required, making them expensive and logistically demanding.
- Programs may function as bilateral or multilateral in destination and origin.
- Linked with the students' future jobs, access to global labor opportunities.
- Students interaction and international exposure is promoted through group assignments, discussions and other activities.
- Offered at all levels (BA, MA, PhD, non for degree. MA being the most common)
- Offered in broad subject areas. Most usual fields: business, management, engineering and social sciences.
- Management, coordination and evaluation of programs tend to get increasingly complex, hence communication among partners is a key.
- Duplication or repeated academic contents as well as task may happen.
- Need for agreement on distribution of academic activities through different academic calendars, grading ad accreditation.
- Some programs foster access for students to research opportunities at two institutions and to diversify and specialize their education.
- Partners may offer joint or separate career support services, E.g. résumé review, mock interviews, research planning sessions, access and orientation to job fairs.

Concrete examples

- In KyotoU: 22 Double and 2 Joint degrees offered.
- In KyotoU: 5 Strategic Partnerships + 11 On-site Laboratories.
- Tohoku University - Tsinghua University in China. Bilateral Masters Degree.
- Florida University: JJ/Dual/DD degrees: inter Dpt. program. E.g. MBA-Juris Doctor.
- Syracuse University: Online Joint/Dual/Double degree: J.D./M.B.A. Program. List of List of Dual Degree Programs and Combined Degree Programs.
- Association of East Asian Research Universities: Global Learning initiative Program (multilateral)

4. Online programs

Features, Pros & Cons

- Remote connection: teaching and interactions happen mainly or purely online.
- Virtual exchanges facilitate communication among geographically distant places.
- Lower cost of implementation, far reaching access and flexible time management.
- Access to ITC tools and quality internet (professors, students, staff).
- Easy access to more educational options due to lack of physical mobility.
- Positive response for continued education especially for people already working.
- Digital literacy development required for professors and students.
- Increasing role and need for technical support and *know-how* is required. Specialized organizations: extra personnel, infrastructure and budget.
- Virtual vs Online: format & learning objectives: Online courses are organized in regular modules, as pre-recorded lectures, activities, and assignments. No scheduled time for lectures. Teachers schedule virtual meetings for interaction. Assignments and activities are administered through LMS (housing the course).
- Virtual courses: closer to schedule in-person courses. Students and faculty meet online, on a shared platform, on preset sessions (dates & duration). Interactions include lectures and discussions in real time. Assignments are distributed in real-time. Email and LMS are widely used.
- LMS and digital platforms house the courses, they include communication tools like messaging systems, forum or discussion rooms, chat, etc.
- Distribution and submission of assignments is online.
- Content is broken down into segments: can be watched later and several times.
- In lectures and interactions are on real time, with email or live chat follow ups.
- Usual examples of virtual exchange: telecollaboration in language learning, online intercultural exchanges, topic specific joint lectures, joint research, etc.
- Issues with QA: domestically in the institution and externally. E.g. National Certificate and Accreditation Agencies.
- Problems with legitimacy. *Trust issues* by academics, governments, employers.
- Access to quality internet by students, professors and administrative staff.

Concrete examples

- In KyotoU: MOOCs at KyotoUx and KyotoU OpenCourseWare
- In KyotoU: Summer/Spring course 2021
- MOOCs as an efficient dashboard platforms: EdX, Coursera, etc.
- Master's degrees on edX. Top-ranked. Affordable. Fully Online
- University of Manchester Global Online MBA
- Monash University English & Culture Course
- Online Post-Baccalaureate Certificates in Health Informatics University of Illinois

5. International joint online

Features, Pros & Cons

- New form of cooperation integrating international, joint and online features.
- Multiple arrangements for degree(s) & partnerships: 1 degree from 2+ universities // 2+ degrees from 2+ universities // 2+ degrees from 1 university.
- Innovation and complementarity in teaching, research, and social engagements base on collaborative environments that relay on reputation of partners.
- Combination of real-time, live online sessions, self-paced learning, on and off campus courses, and experiential learning opportunities.
- Typically function as courses that are credit-bearing and widely recognized that contain hybrid elements of joint teaching, individual teaching, coaching, etc.
- Tend to have multidisciplinary outlooks combining theory and practice.
- Based on agreed curricula that brings together the best of each partner.
- Classes take place in different campuses through exiting curricula with relatively cheap, easy access to education matching students' diverse career goals.
- Wide but centralized catalogue of course options (centralized search engine) for subjects and contents (E.g. *The Jukebox* at university of Tsukuba)
- Active connectivity with peers is promoted through different platforms on subject while promoting exposure to new cultures and the extended communities.
- Shorten timelines and flexible sequencing: customization of time and content. Combinations of online and in-person instruction through ITC and educational technology platforms boost direct connections and *active learning* strategies
- Students gain access to services like academic counseling, study groups, exam preparation, professional development.
- Blended learning produce deep students' engagement and learning outcomes. It can add in-person mentorship, peer learning, group work and social interaction.
- Important pedagogical challenges exist and technology literacy is required. Coordination and mutual technical support for delivery is needed
- Personal & institutional commitments are necessary to avoid burnout and dropout.
- Complex arrangement are need to agree on distribution of task and activities based on shared goals and adjustment to mutually beneficial academic calendar
- Issues with academic credits, virtual examinations, and legal recognition of degrees
- Need for strong institutional commitment for sustainable partnerships an support.
- Resources tend to be more unstable as multiple players take part.

Concrete examples

- 3 European countries 1 joint PhD Diploma Online: OUS Royal Academy of Economics and Technology (Switzerland), University of Dąbrowa Górnicza (Poland) & Taras Shevchenko National University (Ukraine)
- IARU: Joint Online Course. Cambridge, National University of Singapore, UC Berkeley, and The University of Tokyo. Focus: State Fragility and Peacemaking
- Universities using edX Online Campus as digital Teaching Assistant to optimize in-person time for mentorship, reinforce ideas, and foster connection of students.

6. COIL: an integral response

Features, Pros & Cons

- COIL (Collaborative Online International Learning) is Integrated strategy developed in 2014 at State University of New York. It is a new pedagogic method that allows universities to connect with partners to broaden their teaching capabilities: coordinated teaching through the use of ITC to connect learners in different countries, boosting exposure and specific academic learning. Courses comply with legal requirements of each country.
- Hybrid learning combining distance learning with actual and virtual mobility. *COIL+* methodology can be applied before, during and after study abroad programs.
- Within a limited time and budget, COIL courses offer cost-effective ways to heighten students' intercultural competence.
- Reduced costs due to reduced actual mobility. Other costs such as ZOOM, storage space for videos, communication apps. Distribution of costs: academic and logistics varies depending on nature, scope and length of program.
- Students engage on cross-cultural interactions and collaborative educational programs online, developing intercultural competences, 21st Century Skills, and hands-on experience.
- May relate to MOOCs as a base for theoretical learning but with direct interaction
- COIL may be included as part of the overall internationalization strategy of the university. Internationalization at home effects E.g. joint development of curricula.
- Virtual exchanges are embedded in the curricula to promote 21st century competence as learning outcomes (intercultural mindset, critical thinking, teambuilding skills, etc.).
- BEVI (Beliefs, Events, and Values Inventory) approach to evaluation of program: to develop pedagogical aptitude, identifying transformation Intervention timing.
- Successful group learning activities require positive interdependence among group members, individual accountability, face-to-face interactions, and learning social skills.
- Regardless of specific areas, COIL promotes cultural exchange and exposure. Can focus on a single discipline or cross disciplines (different fields together on a project).
- Time : One-time virtual exchange; Enhanced (several weeks), Extended (semester).
- Access to wider networks and engagement and meaningful connections.
- Facilitates international recruitment and increases visibility in university rankings.
- Mutual discovery and innovation in research.
- Integrate COIL into the general view of the university (avoid *Dejima* effect).
- Careful with *COIL NOT*: simple MOOC, social media, distance education and distance learning courses, unmoderated programs, programs with not sustained pedagogy
- Interaction type: class-to-class participation; individual vs. class or group participation, opportunities for self-viewing. Enlarge class appearance view as much as possible.

Collaborative Online International Learning

"COIL is likely to provide for more productive interactional opportunities in that individual students will be more visible, hearable and accountable to educators and perhaps more importantly each other (e.g., through minimization of social loafing, increased social facilitation, greater shared affiliations)."

Ikeda,

K. Kansai University

Steps to create a COIL

- **Planning:** (1) Connect with partners; (2) Define learning outcomes and assessment; (3) Determine communication tools; (4) Agree on calendar; (5) Block out exchanges (asynchronous or synchronous); (6) Lessons plan: icebreakers, contents delivery and interactions (virtual and actual).
- **Execution:** (7) Enacting activities through communication tools and keep up with deadlines; enact communication plan and tools, deliver contents, use of LMS and ICT; (8) Assess based on activities and outcomes.
- **Follow up:** 9. Assess overall implementation, report, and re-shape
- **Special considerations:** (1) if your students are suited for COIL; (2) if your course is suitable for COIL; (3) if COIL will stimulate the learning you expect among students; (4) Build your COIL community on campus: workshop to raise interest and engagement; (5) Regular encounters to plan and implement it; (6) Ensure ICT support and mentorship.

3 Tracks approach and 1 example

	Kansai University	James Madison University
Country	Japan (Osaka)	US (Virginia)
Time zone	Japan Standard Time (JST) UTC+9 *14h ahead of Virginia	Eastern Standard Time (EST) UTC-5
Course Title	Field Based Learning	Making Sense of Beliefs and Values: a Guided Tour for Global Citizens
Instructor(s)	BYSOUTH, Don and IKEDA, Keiko	Jennifer Wiley
Number of Students	10	19
Language	English only	English only
COIL Exchange Duration	6 weeks October 14th ~ November 11th, 2018	
Mode of Communication	Asynchronous and synchronous	
ICT tools	Padlet, Flipgrid, Partially ImmerseU	

Table 1. General information on JMU-KU COIL 2018.

Concrete examples

- Kansai University and Fashion Institute of Technology. COIL+ Program: Going Beyond a Virtual Exchange in a Blended Mobility Project
- SUNY's Global Partner Network
- MULTILATERAL COIL: UMAP-COIL Joint Honors Program.
- Kyoto Institute of Technology. Sugar initiative in Design school SUGAR Network
- Sophia-Shizuoka Study tour: Hybrid online-offline and local-global "Japanology: Science and Society".
- Comparative Research COIL Project on "Peace". Morito Institute of Global Higher Education, Hiroshima University.
- Chiba University: Inter-University Exchange Project: COIL Japan U.S. Unique Program.

7. Key programs at KyotoU

- **Top global initiative. Japan Gateway:** Kyoto University Top Global Program
Social Sciences and Humanities: 3 graduate schools (Economics, Letters & Agriculture)
International collaborative educational and degree programs.
- **Joint Degree Ma. of Arts in Transcultural Studies.** GS of Letters with Heidelberg University.
- **Double Degree Doctoral Programme in Economic and Social History.** GS of Economics and University of Glasgow + Wageningen University, University of Strasbourg, University of Göttingen and Chulalongkorn University.
- **Joint International Doctoral Program: Human Biosciences.** KyotoU-McGill International Collaborative School in Genomic Medicine. American & European universities : McGill University, University of Bordeaux, Pasteur Institute, Imperial College London.
- **Intensive lecture courses by KyotoU faculty & partners abroad.** Chemistry & Chemical Engineering: 6 Departments at GS Engineering with partners, E.g. MIT.
- **Joint research guidance in Mathematics:** KyotoU faculty and researchers from overseas partners co-supervise, graduate students research for doctoral dissertations.
- **Combined Environmental Studies.** Comprising the Hall of Global Environmental Research, GS of Global Environmental Studies and GS of Agriculture, on various fields, including natural sciences, social sciences and humanities. Inviting researchers from Ohio State University and Lille University. **Double-degree programs** with Mahidol University and Bogor Agricultural University. **International internship** programs.
- **Public Health Program.** KyotoU's School of Public Health promotes interdisciplinary and international educational programs research and internationalization of degree programs collaborating with universities in ASEAN, East Asia, America and Europe.
- **Double Master Degree Program + Internship.** GSGES and Environmental and Water Resource Engineering with Mahidol University.
- Kyoto University School of Public Health. International Programs. (1) Double Degree Program for Master's Degree with Chulalongkorn University, University of Malaya, Mahidol University, and National Taiwan University. And (2) **Super Global Course: a single-degree program under joint supervision.**
- **International Program on Resilient Society Development under Changing Climate.** (RSDC) at KyotoU's GS of Engineering with various partners in Asia.
- KyotoU DPRI engagement an activities with the global network GADRI: Global Alliance of Disaster Research Institutes
- KyotoU's engagement with **Asian Platform for Global Sustainability & Transcultural Studies** (AGST) Programme of 6 modules: (1) Environmental Policy & Rural Development Studies; (2) Business History & Industry Policy Studies; (3) Developing & Emerging Economies Studies; (4) International Trade & Financial Studies; (5) Business Management & Accounting Studies; and (6) Asian & Transcultural Studies. Partner institutions collaborate to develop teaching materials for jointly implemented courses.
- KyotoU's engagement with edX on provision of MOOCs & OCW
- KyotoU's participation in networks: USRN (e.g. Research attachment), HEKKSAGON, UAW on staff staff, etc.

8. Double & Joint degree Programs at KyotoU (as of April 2020)

Double Degree Programs

Place	Partner institution	KyotoU GS	Degree offered
China	Tsinghua University	Global Environmental Studies	Master's
	Zhejiang University	Energy Science	Doctoral
France	École des Hautes Études en Sciences Sociales (EHESS)	Letters	Doctoral
	École Normale Supérieure de Lyon	Science	Doctoral
	Université de Bordeaux	Energy Science	Doctoral
Indonesia	Bogor Agricultural University	Agriculture	Master's
	Gadjah Mada University	Global Environmental Studies	Master's
	Institut Teknologi Bandung	Agriculture	Master's
	Institut Teknologi Bandung	Agriculture	Master's
Malaysia	University of Malaya	Public Health, Medicine	Master's (Professional)
		Energy Science	Master's
Taiwan	National Taiwan University	Public Health, Medicine	Master's (Professional)
		Agriculture	Master's
		Management	Professional
Thailand	Chulalongkorn University	Public Health, Medicine	Master's (Professional)
		Energy Science	Master's
	Kasetsart University	Agriculture	Master's
	King Monkhut's University of Technology T.	Energy Science	Master's
	Mahidol University	Public Health, Medicine	Master's (Professional)
UK	University of Glasgow	Global Environmental Studies	Master's
USA	Cornell University	Economics	Doctoral
		Management	Professional

Joint Degree Programs

Place	Partner institution	KyotoU GS	Degree offered
Canada	McGill University	Medicine	Doctoral
Germany	Heidelberg University	Letters	Master's

9. Decision making chart.

A course fit for KyotoU (1)

Type	For degree	Non for degree			
Provision	Unilateral	bilateral	Multilateral		
Direction	Outbound	Inbound	Both		
Level	Undergrad	Masters	Doctor		
Contents	Specific field	General	Lang & cult		
Audience	For partners	Open	Mix		
Credits	For credit	Not for credit			
Fee	Free	Free for partners	Pay for all		
Resources	External support	Domestic only	Mix		
Modality	Pure online	Hybrid	COIL		
Partner 1	Bilateral	Multilateral			
Partners 2	SP	Uni. level	Dpt. level	Both	
Partners 3	Partner networks	Other Networks	Other organizations		
Length	compact	short	Sem	Year	Other

Decision making chart

A course fit for KyotoU (2)

10. Options & suggestions for KyotoU

Existing resources in KyotoU

- Experience with online teaching ☑ MOOC & OCW
- Existing courses at all levels (Ba, Ma, Ph)
- Accumulated teaching experience for international courses
- Strong technical support (ICMM + CPEHE)
- Strong partnerships (general MOUs, SEAs)
- Strategic Partnerships + On-site Laboratories
- Support and engagement from alumni organizations abroad

Suggestions for Existing programs

- Consolidate existing programs and raise visibility ☑ centralized marketing plan (HQ)
- *Onlinize* some of the existing programs. E.g. Spring /Summer Kyoto School (ILAS)
- Promote *systemic hybridization*. E.g. Double Ma degree with Mahidol University (GSGES)
- *COILize* existing programs. E.g. Doctoral Degree with University of Glasgow (GS Economics) or Professional Degree with Cornell University (GS Management)
- Incentivize *MOOC development*
- Japanese language and culture online courses for partners (ILAS)

Suggestions for new programs

- Promote the creation of new Online programs like Spring/Summer program, both with general and specific contents ☑ Support needed? Incentive?
- Systematic exploration of partners' intentions for expansion or consolidation of programs, both at university and Department levels. ☑ Start with already existing programs
- Systematic exploration of potentials with Strategic Partners. Including both thematic specific and general or cultural programs.
- Systematic exploration of opportunities with partners of On-site Laboratories
- Explore opportunities for joint programs (bilateral and multilateral) with university networks KyotoU is affiliate with: AUN/ASEAN+3 UNet, HeKKSaGOn, RENKEI, USJI, USR Network and UAW. Wide range of possibilities for educational programs, E.g. including but not limited to: exchange courses, cultural and topic specific, workshops, short and mid-term exchange programs for students including research and internship.
- Similarly explore multilateral opportunities with international consortia such as The Asian Platform for Global Sustainability & Transcultural Studies (AGST), AEARU or GADRI.
- With USRN: consolidate and expand Research Attachment. Strong interest from partners on natural and human Caused disasters.
- Consider dual degrees within Kyoto University: 2 degrees from different Departments. (Interdisciplinary joint degrees) E.g. Ma. in Environmental Resources (GSGES) + MBA (GS Management) // Language (ILAS) + Int'l business (GS Management) // Etc.
- Much interest from NTU & UHH for a tripartite strategic alliance. E.g. general for SDGs or specific in Physics.

Service learning online at Shishukan

KyotoU – University of Florida cooperation in Engineering

11. Broad ideas, challenges & issues

Broad ideas

- Promote a systematic approach and introduction to COIL as a university wide strategy. (KyotoU internal networking to gain Departments engagement for academic contents, plus admirative and technical support support). E.g. following the example of Chiba university, making it a requirement for 1 credit hour in a subject related to Japan International studies
- Online Japan ASEAN Students engagement for SGGs (similar approach to ASEAN Café for cultural learning and the Global Agenda Debate course at the TAG-AIMS Program. University of Tsukuba.

Domestic challenges in KyotoU

- Finding Departments willing to create or adapt to online joint international programs
- Dispersion of efforts and available resources (HQ – Departments)
- Internal regulations
- Sustainability of programs (partnerships and funding)
- Technical support for professors and students
- Distribution of fees and costs among partners and payable courses by students

Legal and external challenges

- Regulations set by MEXT. E.g. on diplomas, credits, QA, evaluation, etc.
- Legal issues for universities “non for profit”
- More difficult in some academic fields E.g. Medical and law schools.
- Finding the right partners. Compatibility of goals and prestige management.
- Margin and flexibility for the planning courses and programs.
- Matching definitions and values of degrees.
- Academic calendar matching, time constraints. Agreeing on length of courses.
- Workload distribution of teaching commitment and credit recognition.
- Communication with partners and students.
- Language proficiency of teachers and students.
- Communication apps that fit all needs; technical issues and internet stability
- Financial burden of courses and its distribution among partners and students.
- Failure as as a source of learning to for future endeavors.
- Saturation of the market
- Ensuring sustainable funding
- Cyber security.
- Etc.

12. References

Programs and References in KyotoU

Japan Gateway: Kyoto University Top Global Program. Program Summary

<https://tgu.mext.go.jp/en/universities/kyoto-u/index.html>

The AGST Overseas Challenge Programme

<https://tgu.mext.go.jp/en/universities/kyoto-u/news/2019/04/003033.html>

KyotoUx. Free online courses from Kyoto University

<https://www.edx.org/school/kyotoux>

Double/joint degree programs at KyotoU

https://www.kyoto-u.ac.jp/en/education-campus/education_and_admissions/jddd

Overseas Partner Institutions

<https://www.oc.kyoto-u.ac.jp/agreement/en/mou/>

University-level student exchange partners

https://www.kyoto-u.ac.jp/en/education-campus/education_and_admissions/non-degree-programs/exchange-students/list_of_univ.html

Academic Exchange Agreements between Departments/ Faculties

<https://www.oc.kyoto-u.ac.jp/agreement/en/faculty-mou/>

Strategic Partnerships

<https://www.oc.kyoto-u.ac.jp/agreement/en/sp/>

On-site Laboratories

<https://www.kyoto-u.ac.jp/ja/about/operation/designation/onsitelab/>

KyotoUx: MOOCs

<https://www.edx.org/school/kyotoux>

Kyoto University Open Course Ware

<https://ocw.kyoto-u.ac.jp/en>

Internship & mid-term report. Master's study in double degree program with Mahidol University

<http://www2.jgp.ges.kyoto-u.ac.jp/news/20190403-855/>

Asian Platform for Global Sustainability & Transcultural Studies

<http://agst.jgp.kyoto-u.ac.jp/aims-and-outline>

2018 Kyoto Global Conference for Rising Public Health Researchers

<https://tgu.mext.go.jp/en/universities/kyoto-u/news/2018/11/002643.html>

Kyoto University School of Public Health. International Programs

<http://sph.med.kyoto-u.ac.jp/info/international-programs/>

KyotoU DPRI engagement activities with the global network GADRI: Global Alliance of Disaster Research Institutes

https://www.dpri.kyoto-u.ac.jp/gadri_secretariat_en/

List of Double and Joint Degree Programs in KyotoU (as of April 2020)

https://www.Kyoto-u.ac.jp/en/education-campus/education_and_admissions/jddd

References

Programs and References outside KyotoU (1)

Tohoku University - Tsinghua University in China

<https://www.insc.tohoku.ac.jp/english/degree/jointeducation/>

University of Manchester Global Online MBA.

<https://promo.manchester.edu.hk/programmes-detail.php?id=1>

Online Joint J.D./M.B.A. Program

<https://jdinteractive.syr.edu/online-joint-jd-mba-program/>

Association of East Asian Research Universities: Global Learning initiative Program

<http://aearugli.weebly.com/>

40 Best Dual Degree Programs [2020 Ultimate Guide]

<https://www.mydegreeguide.com/dual-degree/>

Dual and joint degree programs. Campus France & Campus France USA

<https://www.usa.campusfrance.org/dual-and-joint-degree-programs>

3 European countries 1 joint PhD Diploma Online

<https://www.ous.ch/PhD/?gclid=CjwKCAjwzvX7BRAeEiwAsXExo->

[AL3wRsbZ9VZYQhDdvGmp3op-QRobg2wsQC_OVvcymiEx_Ic53RFRoCA_oQAvD_BwE](https://www.ous.ch/PhD/?gclid=CjwKCAjwzvX7BRAeEiwAsXExo-AL3wRsbZ9VZYQhDdvGmp3op-QRobg2wsQC_OVvcymiEx_Ic53RFRoCA_oQAvD_BwE)

Joint Degree Programs at University of Illinois

<https://pharmacy.uic.edu/programs/pharmd/joint-degree-programs/>

International Study Programs at Tokyo Tech

https://www.titech.ac.jp/english/graduate_school/international/programs.html

IARU. EdTech Horizons Network. Joint Online Course

<http://www.iaruni.org/institutional-joint-working/joint-online-course>

Erasmus Mundus Joint Master Degrees

<https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/erasmus->

[plus/opportunities/individuals/students/erasmus-mundus-joint-master-degrees_en](https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/erasmus-plus/opportunities/individuals/students/erasmus-mundus-joint-master-degrees_en)

Course Jukebox System

<https://cj.tsukuba.ac.jp/>

Syracuse University College of Law faculty. ABA-Approved Online Law Degree Program

<https://jdinteractive.syr.edu/>

Online Joint J.D./M.B.A. Program. Collaboration between Syracuse University College of Law and the Whitman School of Management.

<https://jdinteractive.syr.edu/online-joint-jd-mba-program/>

Johns Hopkins. Dual Degree and Exchange Programs. Two Degrees, Two Networks

<https://sais.jhu.edu/academics/dual-degree-and-exchange-programs>

University of Pittsburgh. Joint degrees

<https://gspia.pitt.edu/Academics/ProgramsandPartners/JointDegrees>

Global Campus of Human Rights. Online courses

<https://gchumanrights.org/education/e-learning/online-courses.html>

NOHA (Network on Humanitarian Action AISBL) International Association of Universities.

Education & Training

<https://nohanet.org/education>

NATO Joint Advanced Distributed Learning Online Course Catalogue

<https://jadl.act.nato.int/CourseCatalog.pdf>

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COIL Activities at University of Shizuoka (US-COIL): Japanese COIL and Domestic COIL

https://www.jasso.go.jp/ryugaku/related/kouryu/2020/_icsFiles/afieldfile/2020/10/07/202010sawasakikoichi.pdf

Global Virtual Exchange Initiative

<https://global.utexas.edu/special-initiatives/virtual-exchange#funding>

Singapore University of Social Sciences (SUSS) Embark on a virtual adventure of a lifetime to Malaysia, the Philippines and Vietnam!

<https://www.suss.edu.sg/news-and-events/events/converge2-create-a-window-to-your-world>

International online schools of samara university

<https://school.ssau.ru/schools>

SUGAR Network at Kyoto Institute of Technology

https://sugar-network.org/universities/Vl16-B8AAB4A6_AO

UMAP-COIL joint programs. In cooperation with Peace Boat.

<http://umap.org/programs/umap-coil-program-list/>

Master's degrees on edX. Top-ranked. Affordable. Fully Online

<https://www.edx.org/masters>

Auckland University. English Language Academy.

<https://www.ela.auckland.ac.nz/online-english-language-course>

ASEAN Café at University of Tsukuba

<http://www.global.tsukuba.ac.jp/tag-aims/asean-cafe?language=en>

Trans-ASEAN Global Agenda. University of Tsukuba

http://www.global.tsukuba.ac.jp/sites/default/files/TAG%20AIMS%20Brochure_o.pdf

Global Society compulsory courses at TAG-AIMS. University of Tsukuba

<http://www.global.tsukuba.ac.jp/sites/default/files/COMPULSORY%20COURSES-Spring%20Semester.pdf>

Auckland University. English Language Academy

<https://www.ela.auckland.ac.nz/online-english-language-course>

<https://www.ela.auckland.ac.nz/general-english>

IARU. Joint Online Course. EdTech Horizons Network: on State Fragility and Peacemaking

<http://www.iaruni.org/institutional-joint-working/joint-online-course>

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Active resources

edX: Scale teaching and online learning for the modern campus

<https://campus.edx.org/>

Udemy. selection of courses

<https://www.udemy.com/>

Coursera: Online courses

<https://www.coursera.org>

COIL Specific

Institute for Innovative Global Education (I-Paper)

<https://www.kansai-u.ac.jp/Kokusai/IIGE/resources/whitepaper.php>

Creating Global Classrooms for Future-ready Graduates. Institute for Innovative Global Education. I – PAPER. IIGE White paper. 2019 April

Learning about Virtual Exchange. Institute for Innovative Global Education. I – PAPER. IIGE White paper. 2019 October

Demonstrations & evaluations of coil practice. Institute for Innovative Global Education. I – PAPER. IIGE White paper. 2020 March

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VE/COIL Initiative in Japan Virtual Mobility between Higher Education in Japan and U.S. and regions beyond: Case Studies and Good Practices. Institute for Innovative Global Education. I – PAPER. IIGE White paper. 2020 September

General interest

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<https://www.newrow.com/lxp-the-future-of-online-learning/>

S. Korea to allow online joint degree programs among universities

<https://en.yna.co.kr/view/AEN20200909008600315>

What are the Different Types of Joint Degrees Available?

<https://www.bestmastersdegrees.com/best-masters-degrees-faq/what-are-the-different-types-of-joint-degrees-available>

Anant Agarwal. Fastcompany. Successful versions of combined online and in-person instruction. A hybrid education format is sticking around.

<https://www.fastcompany.com/90559185/prepare-for-a-blended-future-why-virtual-learning-is-here-to-stay>

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<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9207196>

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Anayat Durrani. Earning a degree – or two – from international universities could make students more marketable. *International Double, Joint Degree Programs On the Rise*

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Guidelines for Building International Joint Diploma Programs Including Double and Joint Degree Programs. (2014) Central Council for Education Working Group on the Internationalization of Universities, Japan

https://www.mext.go.jp/component/b_menu/shingi/toushin/_icsFiles/afieldfile/2015/04/17/1356863_1.pdf

Higher education institutional collaborations: an analysis of models of joint degree programs

<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/pdf/10.1080/1360080032000122615?needAccess=true>

Related books

How To Manage Joint Study Programmes? Guidelines And Good Practices From The JOIMAN Network

<https://www.joiman.eu/ProjectResults/PublicDeliverables/How%20to%20Manage%20Joint%20Study%20Programmes%20->

[%20Final%20Publication%20of%20the%20project/How%20to%20Manage%20Joint%20Study%20Programmes JOIMAN%20Network.pdf](https://www.joiman.eu/ProjectResults/PublicDeliverables/How%20to%20Manage%20Joint%20Study%20Programmes%20-)

a. Overview of project

AREAS

The big picture

- Goal and nature of project

Global trends / Future of HE after corona

- Universities' plans & students expectations

Deliverables: Menu of options

- policy making points for KyotoU

Stakeholders

- Internal and external

Beneficiaries

- Internal and external

Decision Making Chart

13. *The way forward* for KyotoU

Specifics of the project

- The big picture

- BIG GOAL: strategy for KyotoU: synergy + concrete achievements
- Comprehensive Overall framework of stakeholders, actions, expected outcomes
- Nature of project: Multilayer, multiple stage, multiple stakeholders
- Trimming strategy: Hoop, Step, Jump to isolate specific deliverables
 - Hoop: super short exchange programs for culture and language (experiential)
 - Step: exchange programs for credit transfer (Non-for-degree)
 - Jump: research exchange programs + whole educational programs (for degree)

- Global trends / Future of HE after corona

- What universities think and plan.
- What are students think.
- What professors and researchers think.
- Role of online joint international programs
- What can KyotoU do in front of that new scenario

- Deliverables: Menu of options

- INTERNAL: policy making points: encourage action
- EXTERNAL: KyotoU's selling points: engagement
- For KyotoU HQ: in line with Basic Concept: BIG POLICY LINE
- For KyotoU Departments: integrated KyotoU guideline of good practices and opportunities
- For KyotoU Overseas centers: a plan of action for reach out to partners
- For External partners: opportunities they can find in KyotoU: brochure. Website, etc.
- For External stakeholders: opportunities they can find in KyotoU: brochure. Website, etc.

- Stakeholders

- HQ: Multi level (Riji, Bucho, Kacho) and multi sector (Education, international, PR, planning)
- Departments / Individual researchers / students
- Overseas Centers (ASEAN, EU, KUNAC)
- Partners outside KyotoU
- Strategic Partners
- OSL partners
- University Networks
- Students at partners universities
- Students in general

- Beneficiaries

- KyotoU departments and students
- Partners' programs and students
- Students in general

- Decision making chart

- Identify necessary elements to build new policy or new programs
- Rule out unnecessary options

13. The way forward for KyotoU

The stakeholders picture

b. *Menu of opportunities* & action plan

AREAS & issues

1. MOOC & OCW

- University wide approach

2. *De facto onlinization* of existing regular courses

- DD/JD
- Other regular international courses
- OSL
- PS

3. New programs

- Ad hock experiences: new courses created during the pandemic
- Pre existing online courses

4. Regional approach

- Overview of ecosystem issues and opportunities

5. Possible futures

- Systematize experiences
- Enhance centralized support from honbu
- Suggest new possible projects

14. Menu of opportunities & plan of action for KyotoU (1)

Existing resources in KyotoU

- Experience with online teaching ☑ MOOC & OCW
- Existing courses at all levels (Ba, Ma, Ph)
- Accumulated teaching experience for international courses
- Strong technical support (ICMM + CPEHE)
- Strong partnerships (general MOUs, SEAs)
- Strategic Partnerships + On-site Laboratories
- Support and engagement from alumni organizations abroad

- +: Positive aspect
- -: Negative aspect
- S: Suggestion

1. MOOC & OCW

Issues:

- + Strong commitment (technical and institutional) from CPEHE and ICMM
- + Constantly growing and improving OCW platform

- Commitment for MOOC production so far is by individuals
- Lack of domestic awareness in KyotoU of MOOCs & OCW platforms

S: University-wide (Top-down) approach to prompting MOOC development may help ☑
Engage with Hirajima sensei

S: Promote DEPARTMENT LEVEL engagement ☑ engage not only with professors but with DEANS to produce complete PROGRAMS (not just courses)

S: Explore the idea of "MINI-MASTERS"

S: Promote CPEHE's KOALA and SPOC: <https://www.highedu.kyoto-u.ac.jp/connect/en/projects/koala/>

Bridging CPEHE's work on OCW with other Departments in KyotoU

Engage with CPEHE to promote these actions from HQ as university wide

Raising awareness on MOOC through IPM and other university wide channels.

+ Existing programs (Ba, Ma, Ph) were carried online in 2020 due to COVID:

S: Create a systematic approach: be it virtual courses or as online courses.

S: University wide survey: what was done? Would you be interested in continuing as a regular course. Then offer necessary support.

S: Explore interest among existing partnerships (MOUs, SEAs) to create new programs.

S: Extend and expand current MOOC on USR: new contents, new partners.

S: Explore interest among USRN members to create a new joint international online course on Universities Engagement and Contributions towards the achievement of SDGs

Strategic Partnerships + On-site Laboratories

Support and engagement from alumni organizations abroad

14. Menu of opportunities & plan of action for KyotoU (2)

2. *De facto* onlinization of existing regular courses

- +: Positive aspect
- -: Negative aspect
- S: Suggestion

Suggestions for Existing programs

- + : The pandemic pushed ALL international programs in KyotoU to go online.
- + : Accumulated experience: delivery of contents & technical aspects
- : Dispersion of efforts and poor internal communication

2.1. S: From HQ consolidate existing programs and raise visibility of programs

☑ S: Existing programs that have been de facto online can be systematically built to HYBRID programs. While actual mobility will eventually return, making a systematic advancement to hybrid implementation.

☑ S: Headquarters: round of consultation with the Departments in charge of these programs to check on their intensions to promote hybridization. This will require checking with *THEIR* partners too.

☑ S: Headquarters: can organize a workshop for Departments to share their experiences and lessons learned. Consolidate those ideas and together work on a University wide scheme for Systematic Hybridization.

☑ S: centralized marketing plan: specific website

2.2. S: Promote systemic hybridization of existing Joint and Double Degree programs

☑ S: Promote introduction of COIL system to existing programs.

☑ E.g. Doctoral Degree with University of Glasgow (GS Economics) or Professional Degree with Cornell University (GS Management)

☑ S: COIL awareness campaign in KyotoU through workshops.

2.3. Explore intentions for online courses at the On-site Laboratory level.

☑ Questionnaire from Headquarter: to check on intensions and how HQ can support (e.g. recruiting)

14. Menu of opportunities & plan of action for KyotoU (2)

3. New programs

- +: Positive aspect
- -: Negative aspect
- S: Suggestion

Programs created are a REACTION to COVID-19

Spring / Summer Kyoto School (ILAS).

This is an AD HOC mainly cultural program tailored for PARTNER universities.

This program can be done on a more sustainable and permanent fashion. This can also be offered to non-partners universities and making it for profit with a participation fee (after April) .

Systematize experiences from

- ☒ GS of Energy: cultural event on origami
- ☒ GS Agriculture: virtual tour of campus
- ☒ GS GES: Asari sense's online project on SDGs
- ☒ GS GES: cooperation with Mahidol U

☒ E.g Japanese language programs at KU: online offer great potential in the same way.

☒ KUASU to develop content and HQ can support with marketing and recruitment

☒ E.g. Course on Global Competence carried out by Yoshida Mariko sensei. Same as above.

14. Menu of opportunities & plan of action for KyotoU (3)

5. Possible futures

- +: Positive aspect
- -: Negative aspect
- S: Suggestion

-: Information is disperse about Departments' intentions and interest

☒ S: Explore what Departments wish to do and how HQ can support:

☒ S: questionnaire and workshop: IPN can steer this.

☒ S: Promote the creation of new Online programs like Spring/Summer program

☒ General / Language / Culture / Japan Studies (support needed from different Departments, E.g. ILAS, Law, Economics, Letters)

☒ Specific contents: E.g. Departments of Agriculture, Engineering

☒ Interest and Support needed? Incentive?

☒ S: Systematic exploration of **partners' intentions** for expansion or consolidation of programs, both at university and Department levels.

☒ Start with already existing programs: Questionnaire and systematic follow up.

☒ Explore new possibilities: Cultural Engineering with Florida University & GSE

5.1. Explore interest among Strategic Partners

S: Systematic exploration of potentials with Strategic Partners.

☒ E.g. Including thematic specific: NTU & UHH on physics and mathematics

☒ E.g. Cultural or language programs: Hamburg University

5.2. Explore interest among partners in University Networks

☒ S: Explore opportunities for joint programs (bilateral and multilateral) with university networks KyotoU is affiliate

☒ S: Wide range of possibilities for educational programs, E.g. including but not limited to: exchange courses, cultural and topic specific, workshops, short and mid-term exchange programs for students including research and internship.

☒ E.g. HeKKSaGOn or RENKEI

☒ USRNetwork

☒ Proposal for *Joint International Online Course on Universities Engagement and contributions to SDGs* (Attached and to be presented to USRN EC meeting Feb 5, 2021)

☒ Research Attachment: Proposal: Expand (more Departments can be included) and Deepen educational side of the project. There is strong interest from partners in USRN on natural and human Caused disasters

☒ Service learning Online Program at Shishukan

☒ UAW: this can be a program for STAFF DEVELOPMENT (not educational)

14. Menu of opportunities & plan of action for KyotoU (3)

5.3. Bridging with KUNAC

- +: Positive aspect
- -: Negative aspect
- S: Suggestion

1. S: Bridging Demand and Supply on Japan Studies"

- ☒ S: Ecosystem of demand: search on what American universities offer as "Japan Studies"
- ☒ S: Determine what they offer typically to the students and how they get that demand covered (Japanese suppliers)
- ☒ S: Find out in KyotoU counterparts for those programs: E.g. Japanese Language course, courses on Japanese culture, courses on Japanese Society, Politics, Economics and Foreign Policy.

2. S: On-site laboratories

- ☒ S: Explore interest and possibilities in UCSD

3. S: Explore programs for KyotoU students in the US. Mainly language

- ☒ -: So far English language programs are limited to Australia, New Zealand and Canada

5.4. Bridging with ASEAN Center

1. S: Bridging Demand and Supply on Japan Studies"

- 2. S: Explore programs for KyotoU students in the ASEAN: diversity of contents

5.5. Bridging with European Center

1. S: Bridging Demand and Supply on Japan Studies"

- 2. S: Explore programs for KyotoU students in the ASEAN: diversity of contents

13. *The way forward* for KyotoU

The big picture of the project

5.6. Proposal for KyotoU's plan for Joint online International programs

EXTRA MATERIALS

Extra materials (1)

Decision Making chart (compact)

Category	option 1	Option 2	option 3	option 4
Type	For degree	Non for Degree		
Other types	research exchange	Professional training	Internship	others
Level	Ba	Ma	PhD	Mix
Length of term	Compact / short	Midle	long	ad hoc
Contents / field	Specific	Lang & Cult	General	
Degree(s) granted	1 degree / 1 Univ	1 Degree / Vs Univs	2 or mor degrees / 1unv	2 or mor degrees / 2 or more unvis.
Modality	Purely online	Hybrid	Presencial	COIL
Audience	For partners	Open	Mix	
Credits	For credit	Not for credit		
Fee	Free	Free for partners	Pay for all	
Direction	Inbound	Oubound	Both	
Provision	Unilateral	bilateral	Multilateral	
kind of partnership	Unilateral	bilateral	Multilateral	SP
Domestic engagement	University wide	Department level	Mix	
Wider partnerships	Partnering Networks	Other Networks	Other organizations	
Resources available	Domestic	External	International	Mix
Support for students	Financial	Administrative	Academic	Others
Support for partners	Financial	Administrative	Academic	Others
Support for Dpts.	Financial	Administrative	Academic	Others
Academic calendar	joint / coordinated	independent	ad hoc	
Application acceptance	By all partners	By one partner	By a third party	
Application domestic	By HQ (central)	By Dpts. (descentral)	Mix	
Application fee	For free	Free for partners	Free for all	Third party
Legal recognition of degree	National	State / prefecture	Other	N/A
Prior diploma authenticity control	By all partners	By one partner	By a third party	HQ / Dpts
Kind of students	Full time only	other forms of students		
Language requirements	General certificates	Letter from partners	None	others

Universities Engagement and Contributions towards the achievement of SDGs (1)

-TBD with USRN-

Goals

- ▣ Raise visibility of the work and contributions universities in the USRN are doing towards the achievement of the UN SDGs
- ▣ Promote the share of experiences and mutual learning
- ▣ Promote partnership among members in the specific work for each SDG

Targeted audience

- ▣ Students in all fields
- ▣ Researchers and professors
- ▣ University administrators

Format

- ▣ Joint international online MOOC or other similar format

Contents

- ▣ USRN and Individual universities Extra materials (1) practices in KEY SDGs.
- ▣ Introduction of existing projects
- ▣ Design, implementation, and outcomes: Lessons learnt & strategies for success

Focus

- ▣ Educational projects (e.g. Service learning)
- ▣ Engaged Research (E.g. community participatory projects)
- ▣ Other forms of civic engagement (E.g. volunteering, networking, policy advising, etc.)

Academic credits

- ▣ Available but to be decided by each participating university
- ▣ Certificates. E.g. edX certified course

Distribution of tasks and efforts

- ▣ Initial Support on Planning: KyotoU
- ▣ Coordination: USRN Secretariat
- ▣ Implementation:
 - ▣ Leading partner. E.G. If edx: HKPU(?) If coursera USP / UoM / UNSW / YU. OTHER platforms?
 - ▣ Contributing universities: all USRN Members. Universities from outside the Network?

Universities Engagement and Contributions towards the achievement of SDGs (2)

-TBD with USRN-

Strength based on current experience

- ▣ Based on the MOOC experience:
 - ▣ Internal networking and communication
 - ▣ Domestic support in each member university
 - ▣ Technical support of universities doing MOOC or online course

STEPS & DECISIONS (if we do it!)

- ▣ Online Platform (edx, coursera, etc) to host the course
- ▣ “Team leader” and communication strategy
- ▣ Determine TYPE of program. E.g. for Certificate? For Credits? Level: Graduate? Post-grad?
- ▣ Ensure contributors: USRN members + Departments in each university + Technical support
- ▣ Timeline

Existing useful resources

- ▣ Guideline for MOOC [?](#) good to use but needs revision

Connect with external partners

- ▣ E.g. Rankings: THE
- ▣ Other Networks working on USR
- ▣ Other institutions working on academic contributions to SDGs

Available resources & necessary budget: TBD

Effort level: 2-3 hours a week

Level of previous knowledge: Introductory course

Length: 8 – 10 weeks

Extra materials (2)

USRN Joint international online course

Universities Engagement and Contributions towards the achievement of SDGs (3)

-TBD with USRN-

Tentative structure 1: based on SDG number

Week 1

- Introduction USRN
- University impact THE

Week 2

- Best practices SDG# 1,2,3
- Universities A, B, C, D

Week 3

- Best practices SDG#
- Universities E, F, G

Week 4

- Best practices SDG#
- Universities H, J, K

Week 5 ~ 9

- Best practices SDG#
- Universities A, E, H

Week 10

- Wrap up
- The way forward. Tips

Tentative structure 2: based on contributing universities

Week 1

- Introduction USRN
- University impact THE

Week 2

- University A
- Best contributions SDG#

Week 3

- University B
- Best practices SDG#

Week 4

- University C
- Best practices SDG#

Week 5 ~9

- University D
- Best practices SDG#

Week 10

- Wrap up
- The way forward. Tips

Tentative structure 3: based on USR approaches to SDGs

Week 1

- Introduction USRN
- University impact THE

Week 2

- Education projects on SDG# (e.g. SL). Universities A, B, C

Week 3

- Engaged research for SDG #. Universities D, E,

Week 4

- Community engagement on SDG#. Universities F, A

Week 5 ~ 9

- Responsible processes for SDG#. Universities H, B

Week 10

- Wrap up
- The way forward. Tips

Menu of options for Kyoto

DRAFT Ideoonas still to be considered

MOOC

(expansion of MOOCs at Department level)

Reference

Mini master online / SPOC

KoALA (Kyoto University Online for Augmented Learning Activities) is Kyoto University's SPOC (Small Private Online Courses) platform, an online learning environment offering lectures and materials, launched in 2018. There are many different advantages of using SPOC, and KoALA is one of the pioneering instances of SPOC in Japan. Reference

COIL style course: cooperation with UF and Engineering

Reference hybridize

Multilateral course with partner University Network

E.g. USRNetwork on SDGs

Online of Research Attachement

Kyoto Spring School

Pensar en cursos de lengua

Expandir a otras areas academicas.

KUASU courses of Japansese Language

Onliinizar el trabajo de los OSL. E.g. fujii sense in GSGES & Mahidol U

Global competence : ask Yoshida Mariko sensei

Honbu to be nudging for cooperation from Departments. Honbu can serve as a starting point, but Departments will work only with the right motivation: resources and support

Conversation with Iiyoshi: promote mooc , micromaster , spock , eg. The joining management program with management and cornell university